

Some interesting properties of the Smarandache function

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Abstract The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary method to study the property of the Smarandache function, and give an interesting result.

Keywords Smarandache function; Additive property; Greatest prime divisor.

§1. Introduction and results

Let n be an positive integer, the famous Smarandache function $S(n)$ is defined as following:

$$S(n) = \min\{m : m \in N, n|m!\}.$$

About this function and many other Smarandache type function, many scholars have studied its properties, see [1], [2], [3] and [4]. Let $p(n)$ denotes the greatest prime divisor of n , it is clear that $S(n) \geq p(n)$. In fact, $S(n) = p(n)$ for almost all n , as noted by Erdős [5]. This means that the number of $n \leq x$ for which $S(n) \neq p(n)$, denoted by $N(x)$, is $o(x)$. It is easily to show that $S(p) = p$ and $S(n) < n$ except for the case $n = 4, n = p$. So there have a closely relationship between $S(n)$ and $\pi(x)$:

$$\pi(x) = -1 + \sum_{n=2}^{[x]} \left[\frac{S(n)}{n} \right],$$

where $\pi(x)$ denotes the number of primes up to x , and $[x]$ denotes the greatest integer less than or equal to x . For two integer m and n , can you say $S(mn) = S(m) + S(n)$ is true or false? It is difficult to say. For some m an n , it is true, but for some other numbers it is false.

About this problem, J.Sandor [7] proved an very important conclusion. That is, for any positive integer k and any positive integers m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k , we have the inequality

$$S\left(\prod_{i=1}^k m_i\right) \leq \sum_{i=1}^k S(m_i).$$

This paper as a note of [7], we shall prove the following two conclusions:

Theorem 1. For any integer $k \geq 2$ and positive integers m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k , we have the inequality

$$S\left(\prod_{i=1}^k m_i\right) \leq \prod_{i=1}^k S(m_i).$$

Theorem 2. For any integer $k \geq 2$, we can find infinite group numbers m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k such that:

$$S\left(\prod_{i=1}^k m_i\right) = \sum_{i=1}^k S(m_i).$$

§2. Proof of the theorems

In this section, we will complete the proof of the Theorems. First we prove a special case of Theorem 1. That is, for any positive integers m and n , we have

$$S(m)S(n) \geq S(mn).$$

If $m = 1$ (or $n = 1$), then it is clear that $S(m)S(n) \geq S(mn)$. Now we suppose $m \geq 2$ and $n \geq 2$, so that $S(m) \geq 2$, $S(n) \geq 2$, $mn \geq m + n$ and $S(m)S(n) \geq S(m) + S(n)$. Note that $m|S(m)!$, $n|S(n)!$, we have $mn|S(m)!S(n)!|(S(m) + S(n))!$. Because $S(m)S(n) \geq S(m) + S(n)$, we have $(S(m) + S(n))!|(S(m)S(n))!$. That is, $mn|S(m)!S(n)!|(S(m) + S(n))!|(S(m)S(n))!$. From the definition of $S(n)$ we may immediately deduce that

$$S(mn) \leq S(m)S(n).$$

Now the theorem 1 follows from $S(mn) \leq S(m)S(n)$ and the mathematical induction.

Proof of Theorem 2. For any integer n and prime p , if $p^\alpha || n!$, then we have

$$\alpha = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{n}{p^j} \right].$$

Let n_i are positive integers such that $n_i \neq n_j$, if $i \neq j$, where $1 \leq i, j \leq k$, $k \geq 2$ is any positive integer. Since

$$\sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{p^{n_i}}{p^r} \right] = p^{n_i-1} + p^{n_i-2} + \dots + 1 = \frac{p^{n_i} - 1}{p - 1}.$$

For convenient, we let $u_i = \frac{p^{n_i} - 1}{p - 1}$. So we have

$$S(p^{u_i}) = p^{n_i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k. \quad (1)$$

In general, we also have

$$\sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^k p^{n_i}}{p^r} \right] = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{p^{n_i} - 1}{p - 1} = \sum_{i=1}^k u_i.$$

So

$$S(p^{u_1+u_2+\dots+u_k}) = \sum_{i=1}^k p^{n_i}. \quad (2)$$

Combining (1) and (2) we may immediately obtain

$$S\left(\prod_{i=1}^k p^{u_i}\right) = \sum_{i=1}^k S(p^{u_i}).$$

Let $m_i = p^{u_i}$, noting that there are infinity primes p and n_i , we can easily get Theorem 2.

This completes the proof of the theorems.

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